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**ВПЛИВ АНАЛІЗУ РОБОЧИХ МІСЦЬ ТА УПРАВЛІННЯ ТАЛАНТАМИ НА
ПРОДУКТИВНІСТЬ ПРАЦІВНИКІВ ЧЕРЕЗ МОТИВАЦІЮ ЯК ПРОМІЖНУ
ЗМІННУ В ПІДРАЙОННОМУ УПРАВЛІННІ ПІВДЕННОГО РАНТАУ
ЛАБУХАНБАТУ РЕГЕНТСТВА**

**THE INFLUENCE OF JOB ANALYSIS AND TALENT MANAGEMENT ON
EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE THROUGH MOTIVATION AS AN INTERVENING
VARIABLE AT THE SOUTH RANTAU SUB-DISTRICT OFFICE
LABUHANBATU REGENCY**

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Еля Хотма Харахп, Юсуф Ронні Едвард, Енда Новіянти Сіморанкір, Крісті Енда Нділоса Гінтінг. Вплив аналізу робочих місць та управління талантами на продуктивність працівників через мотивацію як проміжну змінну в підрайонному управлінні Південного Рантау Лабуханбату Регентства. Науково-методична стаття.

Це дослідження має на меті оцінити вплив аналізу робочих місць та управління талантами на продуктивність через мотивацію як проміжну змінну серед працівників Підрайонного офісу Південного Рантау, регентство Лабуханбату. У дослідженні взяли участь постійні працівники (державні службовці) Підрайонного управління Південного Рантау, регентство Лабуханбату, загальною чисельністю 30 осіб. Вибірка проводилася за методом насиченої вибірки. Дані були зібрані за допомогою анкетування та документальних досліджень, а потім проаналізовані за допомогою SPSS версії 25 з використанням t-тестів, тестів Собела та шляхового аналізу. Результати показали позитивний і значущий вплив аналізу робочих місць і управління талантами на мотивацію, а також на продуктивність. Мотивація також мала позитивний і значущий вплив на продуктивність. Крім того, аналіз робочих місць і управління талантами вплинули на продуктивність через мотивацію як проміжну змінну.

Ключові слова: аналіз робочих місць, продуктивність, мотивація, управління талантами

Elya Hotma Harahap, Yusuf Ronny Edward, Enda Noviyanti Simorangkir, Kristi Endah Ndilosa Ginting. The Influence of Job Analysis and Talent Management on Employee Performance Through Motivation as an Intervening Variable at the South Rantau Sub-District Office Labuhanbatu Regency. Scientific and methodical article.

This study aims to assess the impact of Job Analysis and Talent Management on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable among employees of the South Rantau Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency. The study involved permanent employees (civil servants) at the South Rantau Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency, with a population of 30 individuals. Sampling was conducted using a saturated sampling method. Data were collected through questionnaires and documentary studies, then analyzed using SPSS version 25 with t-tests, Sobel tests, and path analysis. The results showed a positive and significant influence of Job Analysis and Talent Management on Motivation, as well as on Performance. Motivation also had a positive and significant influence on Performance. Furthermore, there was an influence of Job Analysis and Talent Management on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable.

Keywords: job analysis, performance, motivation, talent management

In an organization, there is certainly a goal to be achieved. One of the factors that supports the achievement of these goals is the individuals or human resources within the organization itself. Therefore, these human resources need to be managed and directed towards achieving the organization's goals. Human Resource Management considers employees as the primary wealth or asset of the organization that needs to be well managed. The South Rantau Sub-District Office of Labuhanbatu Regency is one of the government agencies that plays an active role in organizing general government affairs, coordinating activities for village community empowerment, and coordinating efforts to maintain public order and tranquility in serving the community.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

Improving employee performance in a company can be achieved by attracting talented and highly credible employees who will then be developed and retained by the company, thus enabling organizational goals to be achieved. One effort that can be made to continuously improve performance is by motivating each employee. This is done to show appreciation for each individual employee and to convey the sense that employees are involved and able to support the organization's activities, thereby building added value. Motivation is crucial for employees to consistently provide positive contributions to the company. The low performance of employees at the South Rantau Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency is caused by several factors, namely the lack of talent management in nurturing employees and the insufficient motivation provided to employees, making them feel bored and unappreciated in their work.

One of the efforts that can be made to continuously improve performance is by motivating each employee. This is done in order to provide appreciation for each individual employee itself and provide a sense that employees are involved and can support the course of activities in the organisation and can build added value. Motivation is important for employees so that they can always make a positive contribution to the company.

The low performance of employees at the South Rantau Sub-District Office of Labuhanbatu Regency is due to several factors, namely the lack of talent management in fostering employees and the lack of motivation given to employees making employees feel bored at work and less appreciated.

Based on the phenomenon occurring at the South Rantau Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency, the researchers were interested in conducting a study related to this phenomenon with the title, "The Influence of Job Analysis and Talent Management on Employee Performance Through Motivation as an Intervening Variable at the South Rantau Sub-District Office Labuhanbatu Regency".

The main part

Performance is the actual behavior exhibited by employees as work achievements accomplished over a specific period of time and can be measured in terms of quality and quantity to achieve organizational goals. Here are the performance assessment indicators:

1. Quality.
2. Quantity.
3. Timeliness.
4. Effectiveness.
5. Independence.

Job analysis is the activity of gathering or compiling information about job data in the form of employee fulfillment needs based on skills, abilities, and knowledge as well as the availability of positions to be filled or tasks to be performed. Here are the evaluation indicators for the job analysis variable:

1. Authority.
2. Responsibility.
3. Working conditions.
4. Work facilities.
5. Work output standards.
6. Education and training.
7. Competence.

Talent Management or talent management, is the process of organizing or managing employees that focuses on organizational goals by recruiting, managing, and developing the potential talents and skills of employees. The indicators for assessing talent management are:

1. Recruitment and selection.
2. Retention.
3. Development.

Motivation is the force that arises within an individual to be willing to undertake something to channel their abilities and talents, so with motivation it is expected that every employee will be willing to work hard and enthusiastically to achieve high levels of work productivity. Here are the assessment indicators for the motivation variable:

1. Salary.
2. Supervision.
3. Policies and Administration.
4. Work Relationships.
5. Working Conditions.
6. The Job Itself.
7. Opportunities for Advancement.
8. Recognition or Appreciation.
9. Achievement.
10. Responsibility.

RESULT This research employs the path analysis model to analyze the influence of job analysis and talent management on employee performance through motivation as an intervening variable at the south rantau sub-district office Labuhanbatu regency.

Respondent Characteristics. the majority of respondents were 31-40 years old with a total of 15 employees (50.0%). While the number of respondents aged 20-30 years was 5 employees (16.7%), the number of respondents aged 41-50 years was 4 employees (13.3%) and the number of respondents aged > 50 years was 6 employees (20.0%).

Characteristics of Respondents Based on Gender. the majority of respondents were female with 16 employees (53.3%). While the number of male respondents was 14 employees (46.7%).

Characteristics of Respondents Based on Education Level. The majority of respondents have an undergraduate education totalling 17 employees (56.7%). While the number of respondents with high school / vocational high school education was 10 employees (33.3%), the number of respondents with Diploma (1/2/3) education was 2 employees (6.7%) and the number of respondents with S2 education was only 1 employee (3.3%).

Characteristics of Respondents Based on Years of Service. the majority of respondents have a tenure of > 10 years, totalling 15 employees (50.0%). While the number of respondents who have a tenure of < 5 years is 7 employees (23.3%) and the number of respondents who have a tenure of 5-10 years is 8 employees (26.7%).

Table 1. Results of t-Test for Sub Model I

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	34.172	.801		42.665	.000
	Position Analysis	.059	.017	.280	2.697	.001
	Talent Management	.147	.044	.551	3.340	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation

Source: authors' own elaboration

The statistical t-test results are as follows:

1. The Job Analysis variable (X1) with a t-value of (2.697) > the t-table value (2.05) with a significance probability level (Sig) of 0.010 (< 0.05). This indicates that Job Analysis has a significant effect on the Motivation variable.

2. The Talent Management variable (X2) with a t-value of (3.340) > the t-table value (2.05) with a significance probability level (Sig) of 0.002 (< 0.05). This indicates that Talent Management has a significant effect on the Motivation variable

Table 2. Summary of Model Testing Results for Sub-Model I

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.555	.308	.256	.503

Source: authors' own elaboration

Referring to the regression output of Sub Model I, it can be seen that the significance probability value (Sig) of the two variables, namely Position Analysis (X1) = 0.101 and Talent Management (X2) = 0.002 This result provides a conclusion that the regression of Sub Model I, namely the Position Analysis variable (X1) has a significant effect on Motivation (Z), and the Talent Management variable (X2) has a significant effect on Motivation (Z).

The data above indicates that the contribution or influence of the variables Job Analysis (X1) and Talent Management (X2) on the variable Motivation (Z) is 25.6%, while the remaining 74.4% is the contribution from other variables not included in the study. Meanwhile, for the value of $\delta 1$ can be found using the formula $\delta 1 = \sqrt{1-0.256} = 0.8625$.

Table 3. Results of t-Test for Sub Model II

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	68.253	11.698		5.835	.000
	Position Analysis	.088	.031	.435	2.811	.009
	Talent Management	.238	.092	.452	2.582	.016
	Motivation	.552	.340	.784	4.567	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Source: authors' own elaboration

In the table, the t-test statistics were obtained as follows:

1. For the Job Analysis variable (X1), the calculated t-value (2.811) > the tabulated t-value (2.06) with a significance probability level (Sig) of 0.009 (< 0.05). This indicates that Job Analysis significantly influences the Performance variable.

2. For the Talent Management variable (X2), the calculated t-value (2.582) > the tabulated t-value (2.06) with a significance probability level (Sig) of 0.016 (< 0.05). This indicates that Talent Management significantly influences the Performance variable.

3. For the Motivation variable (Z), the calculated t-value (4.567) > the tabulated t-value (2.06) with a significance probability level (Sig) of 0.000 (< 0.05). This indicates that Motivation significantly influences the Performance variable.

Table 4. Summary of Model Testing Results for Sub-Model II

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.686	.470	.409	.888

Source: authors' own elaboration

The data above indicates that the contribution or influence of the variables Job Analysis (X1), Talent Management (X2), and Motivation (Z) on the variable Performance (Y) is 40.9%, while the remaining 59.1% is the contribution from other variables not included in the study. Meanwhile, for the value of $\hat{\epsilon}_1$, it can be found using the formula $\hat{\epsilon}_1 = \sqrt{1-0.409} = 0.7687$.

The analysis results indicate that the direct influence of Job Analysis (X1) on Performance (Y) is 0.280. Meanwhile, the indirect influence of Job Analysis (X1) on Performance (Y) through Motivation (Z) is calculated as $0.435 \times 0.784 = 0.341$. Therefore, the total influence of the Job Analysis variable (X1) on Performance (Y) is the sum of the direct and indirect influences, which is $0.280 + 0.341 = 0.621$. Based on the calculations above, it can be observed that the direct influence value is 0.280 and the indirect influence value is 0.341, indicating that the direct influence is smaller than the indirect influence. These results suggest that indirectly, the Job Analysis variable (X1) through Motivation (Z) has a significant impact on Performance (Y).

The analysis results indicate that the direct effect of Talent Management (X2) on Performance (Y) is 0.551. Meanwhile, the indirect effect of Talent Management (X2) on Performance (Y) through Motivation (Z) is calculated as $0.551 \times 0.452 = 0.249$. Therefore, the total effect of the Talent Management variable (X2) on Performance (Y) is the sum of the direct and indirect effects, which is $0.551 + 0.249 = 0.8$. Based on the calculation results, it can be concluded that the direct effect value is 0.551 and the indirect effect value is 0.249, indicating that the direct effect is greater than the indirect effect.

Table 5. Results of t-Test for Sub Model II

Variabel	Unstandardized	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Std. Error	P-Value
Position Analysis on Motivation	0.015 (a)	0.019 (S _a)	0.769	0.021	0.441
Motivation to Performance	1.078 (b)	0.314 (S _b)			
Talent Management on Motivation	0.129 (a)	0.044 (S _a)	2.238	0.072	0.025
Motivation to Performance	1.255 (b)	0.362 (S _b)			

Source: authors' own elaboration

The influence of Job Analysis on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable has a test statistic value of $0.769 < 1.96$ with a significance of $0.441 > 0.05$, which means Hypothesis 6 is not accepted where Motivation is unable to mediate the influence of Job Analysis on Performance. The test statistic value of the influence of Talent Management on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable is $2.238 > 1.96$ with a significance of $0.025 < 0.05$, which means Hypothesis 7 is accepted where Motivation can mediate the influence of Talent Management on Performance.

The Influence of Position Analysis on Motivation. The Position Analysis variable has a positive and significant effect on Motivation at the Labuhanbatu South Rantau Sub-District Office. The Position Analysis variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.059, indicating that if the Position Analysis increases by 100%, it will increase Motivation by 5.9%. Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that Position Analysis has a significant influence on the Motivation of the South Rantau Labuhanbatu Sub-District Office.

The effect of Talent Management on Motivation. The Talent Management variable has a positive and significant effect on Motivation at the Labuhanbatu South Rantau Sub-District Office. The Talent Management variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.147, indicating that if Talent Management increases by 100%, it

will increase Motivation by 14.7%. Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that Talent Management has a significant influence on the Motivation of the South Rantau Labuhanbatu Sub-District Office.

Effect of Position Analysis on Performance. The Position Analysis variable has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu South Rantau Sub-District Office. The Position Analysis variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.088, indicating that if the Position Analysis increases by 100%, it will increase performance by 8.8%. Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that Position Analysis has a significant influence on the Performance of the Labuhanbatu South Rantau Sub-District Office.

The Influence of Talent Management on Performance. The Talent Management variable has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu South Rantau Sub-District Office. The Talent Management variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.238, indicating that if Talent Management increases by 100%, it will increase performance by 23.8%. Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that Talent Management has a significant influence on the performance of the Labuhanbatu South Rantau Sub-District Office.

The influence of motivation on performance. Motivation variable has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu South Rantau Sub-District Office. The motivation variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.552, indicating that if motivation increases by 100%, it will increase performance by 55.2%. Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that Motivation has a significant influence on the Performance of the Labuhanbatu South Rantau Sub-District Office.

Influence of Position Analysis on Performance through Motivation. Based on the results of the sobel test calculation, it is known that the test statistic value is $0.769 < 1.96$ with a significant value of $0.441 > 0.05$, it can be concluded that the Motivation variable is not able to mediate the relationship between the effect of Position Analysis on Performance. Thus it can be said that Position Analysis has no influence in improving Performance if done through Motivation.

The influence of Talent Management on Performance through Motivation. Based on the results of the sobel test calculation, it is known that the test statistic value is $2.238 > 1.96$ with a significance of $0.025 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that the Motivation variable is able to mediate the relationship between the influence of Talent Management on Performance. Thus it can be said that the effect of Talent Management will be greater to improve performance if done through motivation.

Conclusions

Based on the research findings and discussions conducted by the researcher regarding the influence of Job Analysis and Talent Management on employee performance at the South Rantau Sub-District Office through Motivation as an intervening variable, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Job Analysis influences Motivation at the South Rantau Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency.
2. Talent Management influences Motivation at the South Rantau Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency.
3. Job Analysis influences Performance at the South Rantau Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency.
4. Talent Management influences Performance at the South Rantau Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency.
5. Motivation influences Performance at the South Rantau Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency.
6. Job Analysis influences Performance at the South Rantau Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency, through Motivation as an intervening variable.
7. Talent Management influences Performance at the South Rantau Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency, through Motivation as an intervening variable

Suggestions.

1. The South Rantau Sub-District Office of Labuhanbatu Regency should pay attention to employees in carrying out tasks and solving problems effectively with guidance from others.
2. The South Rantau Sub-District Office of Labuhanbatu Regency should pay attention to employees in accepting positions with standard work results that align with the job field targets.
3. The South Rantau Sub-District Office of Labuhanbatu Regency should pay attention to employees in participating in the selection process and meeting the qualifications for their positions, following the recruitment and selection stages, resulting in competencies matching their respective fields.
4. The South Rantau Sub-District Office of Labuhanbatu Regency should pay attention to employees in engaging in sufficiently interesting work with high performance outcomes and obtaining challenging tasks that motivate them to achieve better results.

Abstract

This research aims to find out whether Job Analysis and Talent Management influence performance through motivation as an intervening variable in employees of the Rantau Selatan District Head Office, Labuhanbatu Regency. The research was conducted on permanent employees (PNS) at the Rantau Selatan District Head Office, Labuhanbatu Regency. The population in this study was 30 people. Due to the small population, the sampling technique in this study was a saturated sample with a sample size of 30 people. The data collection technique used is primary data in the form of a questionnaire and secondary data obtained through

documentation studies. The data analysis technique uses quantitative data processed with the SPSS version 25 program, namely the t test, Sobel test and path analysis. The results obtained in this study show 1) there is a positive and significant influence between Job Analysis on Motivation, 2) there is a positive and significant influence between Talent Management on Motivation, 3) there is a positive and significant influence between the Job Analysis variables on Performance, 4) there is positive and significant influence between Talent Management on Performance, 5) there is a positive and significant influence between Motivation on Performance, 6) There is an influence between Job Analysis on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable, 7) There is an influence between Talent Management on Performance through Motivation as a variable intervening.

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